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HIV/AIDS and Health Protection Mechanisms: A Review of Literature

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1. Introduction

According to the Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS, HIV/AIDS represents nowadays the principal infectious disease in the world with about 40 million people infected at the end of 2005 (UNAIDS, 2006). The overwhelming majority of those (about 95%) are living in developing countries. In these countries, health protection mechanisms are still far underdeveloped and continue to represent a very limited source of health care spending; they account for only 2% and 15% of total health spending in low- and middle-income countries, respectively. Moreover, contrary to developed countries where exist various forms of public and private health insurance schemes, private out-of-pocket payments account for more than half of overall health care spending (Gottret and Schieber, 2006).

These figures imply that out-of-pocket payments – the most inequitable source of financing – predominates in this part of the world, and therefore, health care financing, in the absence of financial protection from catastrophic illness that insurance mechanisms provide, tends to be highly regressive (Wagstaff, 2002). This entails that the poorest classes of the population bear higher relative shares of the health care cost compared to the wealthiest classes. This may also have potential consequences on overall prevailing income distribution and household living standard (van Doorslaer et al., 2007). In addition, given the wide prevalence of HIV/AIDS epidemic in these countries, the additional direct and indirect cost-bearing aspects, which are imposed by the presence of such illness – e.g., preventive activities, specific treatments and testes, and loss of income– may further aggravate the global negative impact of health expenditures.

Consequently, there has been a great deal of interest among economists, decision makers, as well as international organisations about the possibility of expanding health protection mechanisms in the particular context of developing countries (Carrin, 2003; Preker and Langenbrunner, 2005; WHO, 2001; ILO-STEP, 2001), and broadening health protection coverage to include HIV/AIDS related disease and treatments (Gaumer et al., 2006; Hsi et al., 2002). Although, an ample amount of literature has been accumulated over the last decade on various related topics, little efforts were actually dedicated to assess the feasibility of extending coverage to include HIV/AIDS infected individuals, the potential and actual impact of the prevalence of HIV/AIDS epidemic on the current health protection mechanisms, its

potential impending role concerning the emergence and the implantation of health protection mechanisms, as well as the sustainability of the current financing mechanisms. Empirical evidence on such particular aspect remains hitherto extremely limited.

The main objective of this review is, therefore, to survey the current pool of literature about the inclusion of HIV/AIDS, its impact on the various health protection mechanisms; e.g., Social Health Insurance; Private insurance schemes; Community-Based Health Insurance schemes, trying to identify the feasibility of extending health insurance coverage as a possible alternative to cost recovery schemes through user fees, given the prevalence of HIV/AIDS in the specific country-context. More specifically the review has the following three interrelated objectives:

1. To assess the extent to which HIV/AIDS infected individuals are (ex) included by the current health protection mechanisms.
2. To assess the effect of HIV/AIDS on the main health protection mechanisms.
3. To review the experiences of different health protection mechanisms dealing with HIV, highlighting achievements, strengths and weaknesses.
4. To assess recommendations for better integration of HIV/AIDS related diseases and treatments in health protection mechanisms.

In order to attain these objectives, this review assesses the existing evidence from literature on the extent to which HIV/AIDS related diseases and treatments are included in the current health protection mechanisms. In particular, the research questions addressed in this review crack down on two main aspects that relate to (1) the extent to which the existing health protection mechanisms (various forms of pre-payment schemes and health insurance institutions) provide coverage and financial protection for the target population (individuals with HIV/AIDS related diseases) (2) the extent to which the HIV/AIDS has any effect on these mechanisms (e.g., sustainability of schemes).

This review represents a first step toward a more comprehensive approach that will involve UNAIDS' cosponsors and is aiming at bringing *coherent evidence* and solutions to the inclusion of the response to HIV/AIDS when promoting health protection mechanisms. Consequently, the findings of this review shall inform overall health sector planning and constitute an integral part of the base on which decisions on health care financial protection and HIV/AIDS inclusion can be taken, both at the national and the international level. Ideally,

such decisions should be based on the review and compilation of the available evidence in the literature. However, it should be noted that a review of literature for a specific topic although not aimed at presenting any ‘*original*’ evidence about the effects of a particular programme or scheme dealing with HIV/AIDS, such a study while systematically reviewing the existing evidence as presented by previous studies, shall inform us about the quality of the existing evidence, the extent to which previous findings have brought any evidence related to the integration of HIV/AIDS in health protection systems, as well as the knowledge gap for which further research would be requested. The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 presents the methodology used to survey the literature. Section 3 presents a brief review about various health protection mechanisms. Section 4 provides an analytical review of theory about the insurability criteria as they relate to HIV/AIDS. Results from the literature review are reported in section 5. We end with conclusions in the last section.

2. Methodology

For this review, a wide search strategy for studies is adopted. A search covering all published studies in peer-reviewed academic journals, and the one present in the grey literature including, external/internal and non-reviewed reports is conducted. The search is held using: hand search; searches in electronic databases (e.g., PubMed, Econlit, EconBase, ScienceDirect (Elsevier), Inter-Science (Wiley), Cochrane Reviews (SSServer), SSRN); web pages of international organizations including: the World Bank, the WHO, ILO, PAHO and UNICEF; and iterative reviews of reference lists of papers. The search is conducted using the key words HIV, AIDS and HIV/AIDS in combination with several terms including: health protection; health-insurance; pre-payment schemes; risk-pooling; underwriting.

All searches are performed between October and December 2007. Our initial search has produced an unmanageable number of potential studies, in all several hundreds. A more refined search is then performed by imposing, whenever possible, some restrictions on searchable objects (e.g., geographic location, country income level). The inclusion criteria for this review include:

- Object of study (Intervention): HIV/AIDS and health protection mechanisms/insurance mechanisms; health-related insurance mechanism and coverage for high-risk.

- Outcome or effect: HIV/AIDS inclusion/converge; HIV/AIDS effect/impact and health protection mechanisms.
- Publication: academic journal (peer reviewed); grey literature (external/internal or non-reviewed reports).
- Population: low-income countries; middle-income countries.
- Time period: 1985 to present; and
- Language: English and French.

3. Health Protection Mechanisms

The institutional arrangements and coverage of health protection mechanisms differ substantially across developing countries. Central to understanding and assessing the impact of HIV/AIDS epidemic and its inclusion in various health protection mechanisms is to understand the theoretical and conceptual aspects associated with these mechanisms. This section provides, therefore, an overview of health protection mechanisms.

3.1 Definition

As a starting point, it is important to identify what is meant by *health protection mechanism*. *Health protection mechanism* refers to a series of actions or measures for spreading risks of incurring health care costs over a group of individuals or households through “risk-sharing” and “cross-subsidization” of health care expenditures amongst the participants (Dror, 2003; ILO, 2007). Although this broad definition is not dependent on the particular nature of the institutional, organisational and administrative arrangements that are employed to provide such protection, these mechanisms clearly evoke elements of insurance, mainly *pre-payment* and *risk-sharing* or *risk pooling*¹. They include a variety of financing and organizational options which allow people to cope with their ill health risks through offering them adequate benefit packages (Dror, 2003). Health protection mechanisms can be initiated and administered by a national or regional government; e.g., Tax-based system (TBS), and Social or Public Health Insurance (SHI) system. Under such systems health protection is financed either by taxation (in the form of general taxation or earmarked taxes specifically for health services) or by mandatory earmarked payroll contributions (usually from individuals and

¹ Risk-sharing or risk-pooling usually refers to the reduction or elimination of the uncertain risk of loss for the individuals or households of by combing a larger number of similarly exposed individuals or households who are included in a common fund (ILO 1996, also Bennett et al. 1998)

employers) (Gottret and Schieber, 2006). The broad (or universal) health protection coverage associated with these systems implies that risks are pooled broadly; i.e., without the danger of *risk-selection* (Donaldson et al., 2005). Features such as these give them the potential to be equitable (as they enable health services to be provided according to people's need rather than to their individual capacity to pay), and sustainable (as they enable a broad revenue base) mechanisms for providing health protection to the entire population. By pooling risks and allowing individuals to pay a predetermined amount to protect themselves against large unpredictable medical expenses, each of the above arrangements enables the establishment of an adequate system of health protection.

Yet, in the context of developing countries, especially the low-income ones, none of the above systems is so far well-established or successfully applied (Pauly et al., 2006). This is partly due to the exacerbated poverty conditions prevailing in most of these countries, which cut the way in front of formulating an adequate and solvable system of social health protection (Shaw and Ainsworth, 1996; Ensor, 1999), and the under-developed fiscal systems that hinder simple individual identification on the basis of their contributive capacity (Preker et al., 2004). In addition, constraints on the public sector, low organisational and managerial capacity and the presence of a wide variety of rural and informal economic sectors make control on private resources extremely difficult and complicated (Dror and Preker, 2002).

Given the above limitations on formulating an adequate social health protection system via general taxation or via social health insurance contributions, other alternative funding mechanisms were proposed to help finance the provision of health services in low-and middle-income countries (World-Bank, 1997; World-Bank, 1987; WHO, 2000; Sachs, 2001; Preker et al., 2004). These alternatives include Private or Voluntary Health Insurance (PHI) schemes, and Mutual or Community-Based Health Insurance (CBHI) schemes (Carrin et al., 2005). PHI is defined as any health insurance paid for by voluntary contributions. The latter are usually *non income-based* premiums (unlike the tax and social security contributions). In the context of most developed countries, where social or public health protection coverage is primarily financed via TBS or SHI, PHI schemes either duplicate the public coverage – i.e., covering the same benefits as the public but differing in the providers and quality; or complement the public coverage – i.e., covering cost-sharing under the public programs, or supplement the public coverage – i.e., for services not covered the public coverage (Gottret and Schieber, 2006).

By contrast, CBHI is a particular form of funding arrangement, broadly defined as not-for-profit pre-payment plan that allows members to pay small premiums – voluntary lump sum payments (Bennett, 2004). This form, though evokes elements of health insurance – pre-payment and risk-sharing – but it can still be distinguished from other forms of health insurance schemes, mainly universal/mandatory schemes and voluntary private-for-profit schemes. CBHI schemes are typically characterized by voluntary membership (Arhin-Tenkorang, 2001; Hsiao, 2001), organised at a community level² (Bennett, 2004; Bennett et al., 1998), operate according to core social values (typically are based on the notions of mutual aid and social solidarity), and therefore, they are not-for-profit in their financial operations (Musau, 1999; Atim, 1998; Atim, 1999). Additionally, they are designed to serve people who are unable to get adequate public, private, or employer-sponsored health insurance (Bennett, 2004; Bennett et al., 1998); i.e. people within the informal sector or even formal sector groups, where “formal” social risk protection mechanism is absent, or inefficient.

CBHI include a variety of schemes that have their own terminology or notions corresponding to their initiator, area or scale of operations and/or modalities of functioning (Develtire and Fonteneau, 2001); e.g. Mutual Health Organisation (Atim, 1999), Micro-Insurance schemes (Dror and Jacquier, 1999), and Community Health Funds (Msuya et al., 2004). The administrative and organizational structures of CBHI schemes may vary considerably, but three broad modalities of functioning³ emerged (Atim, 1998; Arhin-Tenkorang, 2001; Jakab and Krishnan, 2004; William, 2001): those formed around health care provider (regional hospital/facility) are characterized by integrated financing and provision functions—called *provider-based schemes*; secondly, those initiated by community organizations (such as cooperative organizations or trade unions) are characterized by separating financing and

² Community-level is defined by geographic location (village, ward or district), professional affiliation (occupations, place of work trade unions or cooperatives, etc...) or clientele frequenting a provider. However, it is important to note that the term “community” has been also used in the literature to refer to different levels of community members’ participation in managing and organizing the scheme; Jakab and Krishnan (2001) have assessed and summarized this dimension.

³ There are different ways of categorizations, Bennett et al. (1998); Jakab and Krishnan (2001); Hsiao (2001); Atim (1998) have all presented different ways to classify these schemes according to different criteria. However, one should be cautious in dealing with various types of categorizations, as the schemes are not mutually exclusive, and there are no conclusive boundaries among them. For the purpose of this review we adopt the one developed mainly by Jakab and Krishnan (2001), as we are interested in the modalities of functioning of various schemes.

provision functions and varying degree of linkages with providers ranging from third party to institutionalized relationships – called *community prepayment schemes or mutual health organizations or third party schemes*, and thirdly, those initiated by the government and then attached to formal scheme – called *national or government-supported schemes*. These schemes, however, cover different degrees of risk-sharing and hence provide different levels of financial risk protection range from high-cost, low frequency events (catastrophic events) to low-cost, high frequency events (non-random events) (Bennett et al., 1998).

In what follows, we briefly review and discuss the main theoretical arguments in favour of promoting the provision of health protection mechanisms via voluntary health insurance—both PHI and CBHI schemes. Similar arguments can be found for promoting such form of voluntary schemes – both PHI and CBHI –, however, given the limits on the former and the rising role of latter in promoting health protection in the context of developing countries, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa, more attention will be paid to the CBHI.

3.2 Theoretical Considerations on Health Protection Mechanisms via voluntary health insurance schemes

Regardless of the various modalities that these mechanisms might take, voluntary health insurance schemes have been presented in the literature (Pauly, 2004; Pauly et al., 2006; Preker et al., 2004), and in the policy recommendations of the international organizations (World-Bank, 1987; World-Bank, 1993; ILO-STEP, 2001) as an “alternative approach” to achieve three main objectives: Financial Protection, Social Inclusion and Resource Mobilization (Carrin et al., 2005). In the literature, several attempts have been made to establish theoretical validations for risk protection mechanisms, mainly those provided via CBHI. These attempts were found to search for a link between the evolution of a variety of voluntary health protection forms and the theoretical development in other related fields such as micro-finance, social capital, and mainstream theories in welfare economics, public finance, health economics, and public health (Preker et al., 2004; Dror, 2001). The link to micro-finance has been established on the claim that the growing experience of micro-finance and micro-credit instruments suggests that the poor can be creditworthy, can save, and can buy insurance (Brown and Churchill, 2000; Johannes, 2003; Ahuja and Jütting, 2003). This argument, however, seems to ignore the fact that the demand for voluntary health insurance might be influenced by factors that are different from those affecting the demand for micro-

credit, for instance, the demand for health insurance is expected to be highly influenced by individuals' ability-to-pay and their incomes, while the demand for micro-credit is stimulated by the lack of income and cash constraint.

Another link, is the one borrowed from social capital theories, suggesting that the long standing existence of “informal” risk-protection mechanisms – e.g., informal financial networks – through families, friends, and local community which form the ultimate safety net for the poor and vulnerable segments of population would play a positive role in making the people joining health insurance schemes (Dror, 2003). Accordingly, the demand for, and inclusion in CBHI is not only influenced by the expected economic and quality gains but also by a set of variables associated with the level of social capital (e.g., social cohesion, solidarity, altruism and trust) in a society (Liu, 1999; Zhang, 2005). Although this argument seems to be applicable in the case of small-scale schemes, it would, however, be less applicable in the case of large-scale schemes. As Bennet et al. (1998) point out that: schemes in which beneficiaries tend to be distributed over a wide area, relatively heterogonous are less likely to experience “*feelings of solidarity*”, rather “*personal risk aversion*” is more likely to form the basis of demand for such type of schemes.

More arguments in favour of such policy alternative are found in Dror and Jacquier (1999), Dror and Preker (2002) and Dror (2003), who argue that the classical conditions of implementing universal coverage health insurance system are not satisfied in the context of low- and middle income countries. This is because the two components of the demand side – *ability-to-pay* and *homogeneity-in-needs* – are too disparate in these countries. On one hand, lower income levels, higher polarization of income, opting out of rich, and the exclusion of a large segment of population belonging to the informal economy are prevalent conditions, when accumulated, they oppose the premise that the *mean* dominates society and that the fringes are composed of a relatively small and typical minority. On the second hand, different segments of the population are at different phases of the epidemiological transition. This situation translates into highly variable *prevalence of illness*, and hence in health care needs between regions within one and the same country, income groups and sometimes even between different ethnic or social group. According to this argument health protection mechanisms via CBHI approach are presented as a way out to surmount the classical problems associated with implementing universal social health insurance, in contrast to the weakness of the *mean* and the *heterogeneity* in the needs among the different population

segments in low-income countries, CBHI is envisaged as a possible way out to validate the two assumptions (dominance of the mean, and homogeneity of needs) within smaller groups of people, composed of individuals selected for their homogeneity at the point of entry into the group. Moreover, it has been argued that unlike the private risk protection mechanisms – e.g., private for-profit health insurance, CBHI does not suffer from problems such as high administration and *transaction costs*, *information asymmetries* and the *mistrust*. The administration costs are low because schemes are administered by the group (or community) members who are symbolically remunerated. Transaction costs are, on the other hand, low due to the small scale of operations – usually all group members live and work in the same area (community). For the same reason, *information asymmetries* – e.g., *moral hazard* and *fraud* – are also limited, as well as the threat of *adverse selection* (Morduch and Sharma, 2002; Loewe, 2003).

Wherever the argument made in favour of these schemes, the theoretical case for using voluntary health insurance to spread the risk of ill health is compelling (Pauly et al., 2006). However, in the context of high-risk illnesses such as HIV/AIDS, the issue of extending health protection coverage via voluntary insurance mechanisms may be controversial. The size of *risk-pooling* that is constituted by these schemes may be incongruous with the “*law of large number*” and its implications, mainly, in terms of the ability of scheme to provide financial risk protection, which is considered to be a function of the size of *risk-pooling* as the health insurance literature suggests. The next section explores insurance aspects for HIV/AIDS and its implications for various health protection mechanisms.

4. HIV/AIDS and Health Insurance mechanisms

Generally, the question of whether certain losses are “*insurable*” and whether insurance techniques are appropriate for redistributing the resulting economic losses are worth further examination. In following sub-section sections, the general criteria for insurability will be reviewed. Detailed analysis of those criteria can be found in (Berliner, 1982; Rothschild and Stiglitz, 1976; Arrow, 1996; Hammond and Shapiro, 1986). While the review provided in this section draws upon such analysis, it does not, however, replicate the depth of that analysis, nor its comprehensiveness, in particular the technical aspects. Rather, this is an interpretative essay to critically assess what can be concluded from the literature about: the insurability of HIV/AIDS; the dynamics that would arise when the HIV/AIDS-infected individuals are

included in risk protection schemes; the effects of HIV/AIDS epidemic on these mechanisms and how these effects work.

4.1 Insurability Criteria and HIV/AIDS: Is HIV/AIDS an ‘Insurable’ Risk?

Risk comprises both the probability and the magnitude of potential losses (in our case health expenditures). An insurable risk is a risk that meets a set of conditions – called *insurability criteria* (Berliner, 1982). An insurable risk must be (Rejda, 1998) (1) random or accidental; (2) defined (3) beyond the control of the insured (4) a large number of exposures subject to the same perils, (5) the peril must be unlikely to affect all insureds simultaneously (6) the loss must be calculable and the cost of insuring must be economically feasible, and (7) The loss produced by a risk must be definite and have a potential to be financially serious (Crocker and Snow, 2000). These conditions are necessary to make risk pooling mechanism of insurance feasible and efficient (Dickson, 2005). However, they are not all independent of one another; while, the absence of one or more of these criteria may not necessarily imply “uninsurability”, the extent to which these are absent with respect to a particular risk exposure, the more likely is that risk to be insufficient to allow the risk pooling mechanism of insurance to operate (Berliner, 1982). Key questions to our analytical review are therefore: **Whether HIV/AIDS meet enough insurability criteria to make risk pooling feasible? What are the implications of HIV/AIDS coverage for different types of insurance mechanisms?**

In examining and discussing the “*criteria of insurability*” for HIV/AIDS, considerable attention has to be drawn to its clinical and therapeutic aspects: the nature of HIV virus, the mechanisms through which it is transmitted across individuals, the creation of vaccines to prevent infection as well as the development of drugs to manage opportunistic infections and conditions associated with HIV/AIDS. Yet, other important aspects to be considered are related to the scale of the disease: its prevalence rate, its incidence rate, and whether or not it represents a major *epidemic* in a region or community.

Initially, when little was known about the virus and no treatment was available, HIV/AIDS, as a pre-existing condition or as an indicator of high-risk, is but one of a multitude of diagnoses that were considered to be “*medically uninsurable*” (Daniels, 1990); its attack appeared to be *non-random* within the general population, and the associated maximum possible loss appeared to be quite high, beyond the level of economic feasibility (Oppenheimer and Padgug, 1986). Indeed, denying access or underwriting coverage (*risk-selection*) practices

with respect to HIV/AIDS has been observed in the context of several health insurance schemes (Diaz et al., 1994; Chollet, 2002). Today, provided the improved knowledge about the disease, the full compliance with ART (anti-retroviral treatment) prescriptions, HIV/AIDS is no longer considered acute, but a chronic “treatable” disease, like diabetes and many other chronic diseases, which are likely to be insured. The question of whether HIV/AIDS meet enough “*insurability criteria*” is worth, therefore, re-examination.

Table 1 provides a summary of “*insurability criteria*” as they may relate to HIV/AIDS. Randomness is used to refer to the requirements that loss occurrence should be *accidental*, *beyond the control of the insured*, and are *completely independent* from other random losses. This implies that all insureds within a given risk pool should have the *similar probability of loss*; i.e., similarly exposed individuals. While the lack of *randomness* with respect to a particular risk exposure might not immediately imply “*uninsurability*”, the greater the level of predictability the more likely is that result (Crocker and Snow, 2000). Whether or not HIV/AIDS constitutes a “*random event*” is, therefore, a central question as it reflects both the extent of uncertainty as well as the probability of loss.

Risk exposure with respect to HIV/AIDS can be seen, at least in theory, as an *accidental* or *random* event, in the sense that no one intends to contract a disease that is almost invariably fatal. The spread of the disease and its rate of incidence can, however, represent a real challenge for formulating an efficient risk mechanism. If, for instance, the *incidence rate* – i.e., the number of new cases in a region or a community during a specified period of time – is quite high, and/or increases at a rate that substantially exceeds what has been previously expected, then there is a high or major epidemic spread. In the context of a major epidemic, risks tend to be *non-random*, perfectly predictable and individuals’ probabilities of losses are no longer independent. This implies that to the extent that the spread of HIV/AIDS represent a major epidemic in a region or community, condition for random and independent risks may fail, and as a result risk protection mechanisms against such epidemic may not be feasible. On the other hand, HIV/AIDS may appear to be *non-random* in the sense that it can be caused by specific individuals’ behaviours, and might therefore be, at least partly, within the control of potential victims; e.g., intravenous drug users or unsafe sexual practices. While the requirement that losses should be beyond the control of the insured is, generally, rarely met perfectly in practice (Crocker and Snow, 2000), the greater the insured's control over the probability of losses, the greater the relevant probabilities of losses to insurance would be.

The condition that there should be a large number of exposures subject to the same perils seems to be fairly met in the case of HIV/AIDS. Indeed, HIV/AIDS represents in almost all communities a threat to a large number of roughly similar, but not necessarily homogenous, exposure units (Rejda, 1998). As indicated above, the *probability of loss* amongst different groups of population might not necessarily be identical – i.e., similarly exposed individuals – HIV can be influenced by specific individuals’ behaviours, and therefore, some groups may be at high risk of HIV/AIDS than others (Berer, 2004). This, however, does not imply uninsurability, but the higher the disparities in the probability of loss among different groups of insured population the more limited the insurability would be. Where the disease is not likely to affect all insureds simultaneously, the existence of a large number of exposure units allows the loss costs to spread over all participants in the risk pool (Zeckhauser, 1995).

Regarding the nature of potential loss associated with the risk, the maximum value of possible loss should be quantifiable (or measurable) (Mutenga and Staikouras, 2007). The insurability criterion suggests that the higher the level of uncertainty over the *collective maximum loss*, the more likely is that risk to be *uninsurable* or *underwritten* (Borch, 1990). As for other diseases, the maximum potential amount of insurable loss due to HIV/AIDS can be now easily quantified and estimated at both individual and aggregate levels (Schwartländer et al., 2001; Walker, 2003). This is because most curative HIV/AIDS interventions and treatments are well-known nowadays, and therefore, their costs can be easily estimated. However, the estimation of the maximum value of loss can be seen problematic at the aggregate level; i.e., the potential collective of affected people. The latter depends on the ultimate spread of the disease; in the context of a major or high spread epidemic, the maximum possible loss may be difficult to estimate, and therefore, the economic feasibility of loss can become an issue for insurance.

Table 1: Criteria of insurability and HIV/AIDS risk exposure

Criterion	HIV/AIDS risk exposure
1. Randomness	Accidental but can be partly within the control of possible victims or transmitters.
2. Loss exposure	Large number of homogenous exposures subject to the same peril.
3. Probability of loss	Higher probabilities of losses causing heterogeneous risk portfolio.
4. Quantifiable loss	Maximum loss is quantifiable at individual level but can be

	problematic at the aggregate level.
5. Frequency and Severity	To the extent that losses from HIV/AIDS are small and predictable, loss amounts would be somewhat certain and premium estimation not difficult.
6. Moral Hazard	Strong incentive to avoid infection. The extent of incentives depends on the availability of preventive measures and collective consciousness
7. Adverse Selection	No incentive to reveal information (major risk).

Frequency and severity of potential losses are, therefore, two important criteria for insurability: frequency refers to the number of claims occurrence regardless of the magnitude, whereas the latter refers to the size of the event, ranging from zero for minor (or small) event to huge amounts for major claims (Schlesinger and Doherty, 1995). Insurance premiums are determined by the product of the two separate statistical distributions reflecting both claim frequency and claim severity (Schlesinger and Doherty, 1995). Generally, risks that are associated with relatively small average losses with relatively high frequency are likely to be insurable – as they are more predictable – than those with opposing characteristics (Crocker and Snow, 2000). Except for major epidemic, losses produced by HIV/AIDS are now definite and predictable, at both individuals and aggregate levels, and, therefore, risk protection mechanisms can rather easily cover for such types of losses. However, the costs of HIV/AIDS interventions and treatments can be high and may not represent to the insurance small average losses. Consequently, insurance mechanisms may face difficulty in setting out affordable premiums.

Moral hazard refers to the possibility that the insured becomes indifferent with respect to the occurrence of loss or even has less incentive to avoid the insured event than before insurance (Winter, 2000). In the case of a fatal disease such as HIV/AIDS, moral hazard may not be expected to represent a serious concern for the insurance. Indeed, given the fatality of such disease, there are in general strong incentives to avoid and prevent the occurrence of losses due to HIV/AIDS. However, the extent to which there are incentives to prevent such an infection depends particularly on the availability of preventive measures as well as the level of collective consciousness about the negative impact of such disease. For the same reason, *ex post* moral hazard, which refers to an increase in *claims rates* due to the propensity of insureds to seek more medical care than they would otherwise (Winter, 2000), is not expected to be a major problem with HIV/AIDS epidemic as is the case with other illnesses. The absence of any moral hazard implies that there would be no variations in the underlying *probabilities of loss* on which the insurance premium was initially based, and therefore, the

trend that the more complete insurance coverage is, the less incentive individuals have to avoid the insured event seems to be less applicable to HIV/AIDS than to the more common varieties of economic losses.

By contrast, adverse selection, which refers to a situation of asymmetrical information between the insured and the insurer, can represent an important issue for insurance (Biglaiser and Mezzetti, 1993). HIV/AIDS-positive individuals may indeed have no incentive to reveal that information when applying for insurance schemes. The presence of information asymmetry implies that high-risk individuals would be able to obtain the low-risk health insurance. The consequence of adverse selection can be significant for insurance as it would affect the allocation of risks and costs, as well as the way by which insurers would choose to price and classify risks. An immediate impact is on the *portfolio of risk pooling*, since individuals at high risk of HIV/AIDS are expected to represent higher probabilities of losses (e.g., high costs associated with the treatment of opportunistic infections, or antiretroviral therapy) compared with those not so affected, significant *disparities* in losses probabilities relevant to a risk pool may arise, and consequently, the condition of *homogenous risk portfolio* fails. The implications of these will be discussed in the following sub-section. Suffice here to note that HIV/AIDS appears to meet several characteristics of insurable risks: its attack appears to be random within the general population, and its losses are comparable to that of insurable diseases. However, the feasibility of risk pooling depends largely on whether or not the disease represents a major or a high spread epidemic in a region or a community. The following sub-section examines the incidence of HIV/AIDS within the insurable population and the implications for different types of health protection mechanisms.

4.2 HIV/AIDS and the implications for health protection mechanisms

The incidence of HIV/AIDS within the insurable population can be illustrated as in **Figure 1**. The outer boundary shows the universe of potential insureds who may be infected with the HIV and who may ultimately develop AIDS. A major distinction within that universe of potential insureds can be made between *high-risk group* and others.

Figure 1: Incidence of HIV/AIDS within the insurable population

Under universal (or full) coverage insurance, the risk-sharing scheme involves participation of the general population of the insured. There is no *risk-selection* due to HIV/AIDS status: the HIV/AIDS-infected group would benefit from the scheme as much as the non-infected group, without the danger of adverse selection. As indicated above, risk-pool constituted by such coverage is a broad one, with all types of risks being merged into a single group and charged the average premium of the group. Assuming that the incidence of AIDS within the insurable population does not change, the total cost initially budgeted by the scheme would remain constant and, other things being equal, the average premium charged would be adequate to cover the losses of the group.

In the context where risk-sharing scheme does not involve the full participation of the general population – e.g., the case of private voluntary schemes – losses associated with HIV/AIDS can be an issue for the *financial sustainability* of the scheme. If, for instance, high proportion, or at least, higher than expected proportion of the scheme’s enrollees were HIV-positive, then the cost of their care would be greater than that initially budgeted for, and the scheme may face serious financial instability unless it can adjust the premiums upwards. However, if premiums increase substantially to reflect the higher cost of care associated with people living with HIV/AIDS, then the scheme may become unattractive for *low-risk individuals* who do

not anticipate needing such intensive use of health care services. Consequently, HIV-negative people may withdraw from the insured group, and the relative cost per capita would be driven up even further in a vicious circle.

To overcome this problem the only mechanism the insurer has to prevent the breakdown of the scheme is to split off the *insured group* and break even on each either by adjusting the premiums to individual's risks; i.e., *premium differentiation*, or by adjusting the accepted risks to the premiums; i.e., *selective underwriting* (van de Ven et al., 2000). The *Rothschild-Stiglitz model* of risk pooling in insurance suggests that full coverage will be achieved only where *actuarial faire premiums* are charged (Rothschild and Stiglitz, 1976). Obviously, the scheme's ability to charge differential premiums for HIV-positive people; i.e., the ability to stratify risk according to HIV status, depends on whether or not there are restrictions or ban on HIV testing. With no restrictions, scheme would be able to apply some form of risk classification (Crocker and Snow, 2000). The latter entails that risks are grouped so that each classification is relatively *homogeneous* in the sense that each insured unit within the class faces approximately the *same probability of loss* (Crocker and Snow, 2000).

The implication of the above discussion is that the impact of HIV/AIDS on health insurance mechanisms depends, other things being equal, on the scale of coverage by the risk-sharing scheme under consideration; i.e., whether the scheme involves a universal or voluntary coverage, and whether in the latter case, risk stratification according to HIV is being implemented. The following section reviews the literature findings about the implications of HIV/AIDS for health protection mechanisms and the extent to which it is included in the risk-pool of various health insurance schemes.

5. Evidence on the inclusion of HIV/AIDS and its impact on health protection mechanisms

Despite a handful of studies analysing and assessing the impact of HIV/AIDS epidemic on various sectors (Lisk, 2002; Plamondon and Cichon, 2002; Bonnerjee, 2003), evidence on the impact of HIV/AIDS on health protection mechanisms, particularly, health insurance schemes, are extremely limited. The extreme paucity of empirical evidence on the subject cannot, however, be interpreted as an indicator of "marginal" or "limited" impacts of the disease on the various formal and informal insurance mechanisms. Obviously, however, the

limited evidence base may signal “*limited converge*” and “*exclusion practices*” with respect to HIV/AIDS from the risk pool of these mechanisms; thus, making them – compared with other sectors – a “less potential candidate” for “large” or “significant” effects of HIV/AIDS (Kamuzora and Gilson, 2007; Sinha et al., 2006).

Indeed, there is some evidence in the literature to suggest that individuals with HIV/AIDS related illnesses are often not included in health protection mechanisms/arrangements. Exclusion of people with HIV/AIDS from the current health protection schemes/arrangements can be seen as a direct result of one of two practices: either by denying access to virtually all of people with HIV/AIDS (e.g., excluding HIV/AIDS related treatments from schemes’ benefit packages), or by stratifying risk according to HIV status (e.g., charging higher and unaffordable premiums). Yet, in most the cases, the exclusion of HIV/AIDS was due to the former practice.

Denying access to virtually all of people with HIV/AIDS has been observed not only in the case of several private and CBHI arrangements, but also in the context of SHI arrangements in some developing countries. For instance, the recently introduced National Health Insurance Scheme (NSHI) in Nigeria has excluded from its initial implementation “*high-cost illnesses such as cancer and HIV/AIDS*” on the grounds that “*the cost of treating these illnesses could wipe out everything that has been collected*” (Okonkwo, 2001). In south Africa, which is experiencing the fastest growing HIV/AIDS epidemic in the world, mutual health insurers (Medical Schemes – private not-for-profit) were recently allowed, by law, to risk-rate the cover which they provide, and to exclude “*medically uninsurable*” risks (Söderlund and Hansl, 2000). In Rwanda, both the official, institutionalised Sickness Insurance Schemes (known RAMA) and the Mutual benefit structure, which is organised around the community, do not provide any cover for HIV/AIDS related treatments, as stated by their amended law these schemes “*cover all medical benefits except for antiretroviral drugs (ARVs)*” (Musango et al., 2006).

In sub-Saharan Africa, HIV/AIDS services covered by CBHI schemes vary (**Table 2**); aside from preventive (e.g., information, and communication (IEC) and outreach activities) most schemes appear not to offer HIV/AIDS services care (Hsi et al., 2002). A survey of 10 schemes in Senegal found that none covered HIV/AIDS services (Schneider et al., 2001; Schneider et al., 2006). In Ghana, six of the eight Mutual Health schemes surveyed did include

HIV/AIDS services, but these focused predominantly on preventive care and support (Anie et al., 2001). The latter survey indicated that while there appeared not to be discrimination against those who are HIV-positive in terms of coverage under these schemes, the two schemes not offering HIV/AIDS are those serving in the lowest-prevalence areas in Ghana with HIV/AIDS prevalence rates being about 1.5 percent (compared to other regions where prevalence is reach 5.3 percent). Such exclusion was interpreted, according to this study, in terms of the lower perception of risk in the lower-prevalence regions. A recent study from India (Mahal and Rao, 2005), has reported similar findings on the wide exclusion of HIV/AIDS from health protection mechanisms: the study found that in general, insurance is not accessible to Indians with HIV/AIDS, due to the low coverage of private health insurance, and presumably, excludability clauses.

Table 2: HIV/AIDS Services Financed or Provided by CBHI Schemes

Scheme	Country	HIV/AIDS provisions	Coverage of population in %
Kisiizi Hospital Health Society (Est. 1996)	Uganda	None explicitly mentioning HIV/AIDS, however could in fact cover outpatient and inpatient care for HIV/AIDS patients	6.5
Chogoria Hospital Insurance Scheme (Est. 1991)	Kenya	Explicitly excludes AIDS treatment costs over Ksh 2000 per year.	0.3
Community Health Fund (Est. 1996)	Tanzania	If a client is HIV positive through test results, clients are referred to national HIV clinics.	2.8 (population in one district)
Atiman Health Insurance Scheme (Est. 1995)	Tanzania	Does not cover AIDS, TB, cancer, hospitalization	13
Mburahati Coop Society (Est. 1992)	Tanzania	Explicitly excludes chronic diseases, AIDS, TB, diabetes	85
Nkoranza Community Health Insurance Scheme (Est. 1992)	Ghana	None stated in benefits package	30
Prepayment schemes (Est. 1999)	Rwanda	Church paid for 50 seropositive members	8 (population in 3 districts)

Source: (Hsi et al., 2002)

Regarding the impact of HIV/AIDS on various insurance schemes, the little empirical evidence that exists suggests that the HIV/AIDS epidemic is most likely to have significant financial implications on the various health protection mechanisms (Bonnerjee, 2003; Plamadon et al., 2004). Clearly, however, the magnitude of such impact can differ significantly across the various schemes to the extent that HIV/AIDS affects the number of contributors, their earnings and contribution rates.

One study on the “*Financial effects of HIV/AIDS on National Social Protection Schemes*” by Plamondon et al (2004) stresses that “*the HIV/AIDS pandemic poses a huge challenge to the financial management of national social protection systems*”. Using a simplified social budget model, the paper examines the potential financial effects of HIV/AIDS on national protection schemes – in particular pension schemes and social security – and simulates possible coping mechanisms. Findings from the study suggest that HIV/AIDS, in general, raises the cost of social programmes and social insurance. The impact of HIV/AIDS on national health protection schemes is simulated using a hypothetical country case and various scenarios. HIV/AIDS is shown to affect these schemes through its overall demographic and economic impacts. For instance, the *demographic impact* of HIV/AIDS can be seen through the *combined effect* of higher mortality and lower fertility on the population structure. HIV/AIDS causes an increase in mortality for two critical age segments of population: the very young (0-4 years) who represent future members of the labour force, and young adults (15-49) who are likely to be members of the labour force, and therefore, contributors of a social scheme. The mortality due to AIDS can also prevent a large proportion of population from reaching retirement age. The consequences of the above effects on the labour force and the aggregate economy are clear; HIV/AIDS affects labour force participation rates and productivity rates, and may thus, have significant negative effects on the tax base for domestic government revenues, as well as the contribution base for social security schemes and pension systems. The impact of HIV/AIDS on these schemes is shown to depend largely on the *replacement rates* –given the fact that in the context of most developing countries there is a high level of unemployment and a large informal sector, the study concluded that the impact of AIDS on national schemes can be *financially manageable*, as long as schemes can find new contributors. Indeed, projections from the social budget exercise presented in the study have shown that although the prevalence of HIV/AIDS may put these schemes in a difficult financial positions, the emerging deficits may not be unmanageable.

A more recent study on the impact of HIV/AIDS on social security schemes came from Zimbabwe (Chikova and Chinamasa, 2007). Results from this study clearly showed that HIV/AIDS and growth of the imposed ceilings on insurable earnings separately and in combination have an important attritional impact on projected contributions to the National Pension and other Benefits Scheme in Zimbabwe. The study projections further showed that HIV/AIDS will reduce projected contributions to the scheme by up to half by 2030, but adjusting the level of growth of the imposed ceilings to a level close or equal to the level of prevailing growth in inflation will optimize contributions to the scheme.

The effects of HIV/AIDS on community-based schemes/arrangements have not hitherto been well documented. However, there are some pointers to suggest that these schemes are vulnerable to the potential risks associated with HIV/AIDS. Indeed, although few CBHI schemes were actually found to include HIV/AIDS related treatments in their benefit packages, the key risk when it comes to these schemes is their financial sustainability, in particular the insolvency risk (Hsi et al., 2002). As indicated above, CBHF schemes are motivated by the notion of “social solidarity” and operate on the basis of open access and community rating. This means that these schemes do not “underwrite” or explicitly “exclude” HIV-positive people from their membership. Some information and evidence can be gleaned from studies on CBHI. One study on the CBHI in sub-Saharan Africa (Hsi et al., 2002) found that the majority of the CBHI were unaware or know very little about the prevalence of HIV in their membership pools. This is because either the local testing capacity is extremely limited, or it is ethically unacceptable for these schemes to require HIV testing. Alternatively, schemes were found to cap the services provided in their benefit packages. Lastly, we find no evidence that HIV/AIDS has affected of the financial contributions of these schemes or has led to financial ruin or insolvency of any of them. This finding might however be partly driven by the extremely limited evidence base on evaluating the impact of HIV/AIDS on this type of schemes.

Finally, we find no evidence on the impact of HIV/AIDS on private health insurance schemes. However, there are reasons to think that the impact of HIV/AIDS on private health insurance schemes may not be as significant as on community-based health insurance schemes, given that insurance companies can screen out HIV-positive individuals from the pool of insurable individuals. It is also possible that treatment costs for opportunistic infections are passed on to third party payers without disclosure of an individual’s HIV status. For instance, one

Zimbabwean insurance company estimated that 45 per cent of its health insurance claims in 1995-96 were AIDS-related (Bloom et al., 2002). However, with private voluntary health insurance in developing countries still in its infancy it is difficult to say what the future impact of AIDS on this sector might be. Potential sector-level responses that may significantly reduce the impact of HIV/AIDS may include added screening to enforce exclusions for HIV/AIDS, or greater participation of insurers in prevention messages and in offering incentives to corporate and other large clients to promote prevention messages in return for more attractive insurance packages, as in Thailand (Mahal, 2002). Should the right to underwrite, or to stratify risk according to HIV status be jeopardized, there might be significant financial implications for these insurance schemes.

6. Conclusions

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